

Development of HAMOD: a High Agreement Multi-lingual Outlier Detection dataset

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Abstract.

In this paper we describe further development of a High Agreement Multi-lingual Outlier Detection dataset (HAMOD) outlier that is used for the purpose of evaluation of automatic distributional thesauri. We briefly introduce the task and methodological motivation for developing such a dataset, then we present the current status of the dataset and related tools as well as results measured on the dataset so far (both in terms of agreement rates and thesauri evaluation). Finally we discuss future developments of HAMOD.

Keywords: HAMOD · Distributional thesaurus · Outlier detection · Word embeddings · Sketch Engine

1 Introduction and motivation

This paper presents new developments of the HAMOD dataset. HAMOD stands for an acronym of *High Agreement Multi-lingual Outlier Detection*, a dataset for exercising the outlier detection task that aims at high inter-annotator agreement. Outlier detection is a task where a human or machine is presented with a set of words (in our case 9), out of which one is a so called *outlier*: a word that “doesn’t fit” to the others.

In [1] it was argued that outlier detection is (unlike the intrinsic evaluation based on similarity judgements) a reliable method for evaluating automatic distributional thesauri. A distributional thesaurus is generally a mapping of pairs of words to a numeric similarity score (or conversely, a dissimilarity score, i.e. a distance) yielding in the first place a list of most similar words for a given word. There are several methods for calculating a distributional thesaurus, such as using word sketches in Sketch Engine [2] or using a vector space model

(word embeddings) (see e.g. [3]). The real difficulty for any comparison and further development of these methods is that a reliable evaluation methodology is currently missing: a directly intrinsic evaluation suffers from extremely low inter-annotator agreement. For this reason we started developing HAMOD in 2019 and continuously expand the dataset both in terms of number of languages and number of exercises.

In further text we describe the dataset itself, thesauri that we used for evaluation so far and our plans for further development.

2 Sketch Engine and the word sketch-based thesaurus

Sketch Engine [4] is a leading text corpus management system which as of 2021 includes several hundreds of preloaded corpora as well as corpus-building functionalities available for regular end users. The preloaded corpora typically come from the web and aim at targeting multi-billion size. In 2010, Sketch Engine started the so-called TenTen series of web corpora [5], aiming at building a corpus of ten billion words (10^{10} , thus “TenTen”) for as many languages as possible.

A word sketch is a short summary of a word’s collocational behaviour from the perspective of individual grammatical relations (noun’s modifier, verb’s subject etc.), as can be seen from the example given in Figure 1.

modifiers of "account"	nouns modified by "account"	verbs with "account" as object	verbs with "account" as subject
bank 88,271 ... bank account	holder 10,883 ... account holders	open 26,686 ...	belong 955 ... accounts belonging to
twitter 35,635 ... Twitter account	deficit 7,635 ... current account deficit	create 50,014 ...	balance 348 ... account balances
email 24,059 ... email account	balance 9,838 ... account balance	delete 5,276 ...	differ 528 ... accounts differ
user 26,077 ... user account	receivable 3,912 ... accounts receivable	register 5,661 ...	unbanned 298 ... to have the account u...
checking 10,970 ... checking account	executive 8,498 ... Account Executive	access 7,391 ...	open 1,295 ... account opened
facebook 13,512 ... Facebook account	manager 21,579 ... Account Manager	manage 11,442 ...	exist 960 ... into account existing
detailed 13,386 ... a detailed account of	password 3,362 ... account password	check 5,122 ...	expire 322 ... account has expired
paypal 8,434 ... PayPal account	surplus 2,371 ... current account surplus	close 5,161 ...	allow 1,716 ... account allows you
		activate 2,851 ...	
		link 4,179 ... note that Education ...	
		take 48,517 ... take account of	

Fig. 1: An example of a word sketch for the English noun *account*.

Each word sketch item is a triple consisting of the headword, the grammatical relation and the collocate. As such a word sketch is basically a dependency syntax graph, calculated using a hybrid rule-based and statistical approach. The

backbone word for computing word sketches represents a hand-written word sketch grammar, which selects collocation candidates using the corpus query language (CQL, [6]).

A sketch grammar typically makes heavy use of regular expressions over morphological annotation of the corpus to select syntactically viable collocation candidates. These candidates are subsequently subject to statistical scoring using a word association score. LogDice is used as the association metric in Sketch Engine as it was proven to be scalable across corpora of different sizes and produces scores comparable across corpora too [7].

Word sketches make it possible to automatically derive a distributional thesaurus by calculating similarity of word sketch contexts: for each word, we look at which other words share most collocates (in the same grammatical relations).

To compute a similarity score between word w_1 and word w_2 , we compare w_1 and w_2 's word sketches in this way:

- find all the overlaps, i.e. where w_1 and w_2 share a collocation in the same grammatical relation, e. g.: (*beer/wine*, *OBJECT_OF*, *drink*), where the association score > 0 ,
- let ws_{w_1} and ws_{w_2} be the set of all word sketch triples (*headword*, *relation*, *collocation*) for w_1 and w_2 , respectively, where the association score > 0 ,
- let $ctx(w_1) = \{(r, c) | (w_1, r, c) \in ws_{w_1}\}$,
- let AS_i be the association score of a word sketch triple (logDice),
- then the distance between w_1 and w_2 is computed as:

$$Dist(w_1, w_2) = \frac{\sum_{(r,c) \in ctx(w_1) \cap ctx(w_2)} AS_{(w_1,r,c)} + AS_{(w_2,r,c)} - \frac{(AS_{(w_1,r,c)} - AS_{(w_2,r,c)})^2}{50}}{\sum_{i \in ws_1} AS_i + \sum_{i \in ws_2} AS_i}$$

The term $(AS_i - AS_j)^2/50$ is subtracted in order to give less weight to shared triples, where the triple is far more salient with w_1 than w_2 or vice versa. We find that this contributes to more readily interpretable results, where words of similar frequency are more often identified as near neighbours of each other.

A thesaurus screenshot from Sketch Engine can be found in Figure 2.

3 Thesaurus built from word embeddings

Another method, or rather a whole paradigm, that can be used for deriving an distributional thesaurus, is based on calculating a vector representation for each word in a corpus (so called word embedding) and using the distances between individual word vectors as a measure of words' (dis)similarity. For our experiments we used FastText [8] and Word2vec [3] to calculate word embeddings based on corpora available in Sketch Engine [9].

A screenshot from the web interface used for evaluation is provided in Figure 3. In each turn of the exercise, evaluators select the outlier, or may skip the turn if they are unsure. Currently HAMOD contains 38 complete exercise sets and the target size for all languages is 100.

5 Evaluation

Initial evaluation of the inter-annotator agreement for Czech and Estonian shows very promising results as it exceeds 90 % of absolute raw agreement (chance-correction does not play a big role: with 10 annotators and 8 options chance agreement is $\frac{1}{8}^{10} < 10^{-10}$). Detailed agreement figures for both languages are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Inter-annotator agreement for languages included in HAMOD. A success run means an exercise where all sets were correctly fulfilled by an evaluator.

Language	Success runs	All runs	Agreement
Czech	2,082	2,150	0.97
Estonian	3,285	3,525	0.93

Evaluation of two distributional thesauri by means of overall accuracy (where the outlier was correctly identified) and outlier position percentage (OPP, average percentage of the right answer) is provided in Table 2. We used the czTenTen12, deTenTen13, enTenTen13, frTenTen12, itTenTen16, skTenTen11 [5] and EstonianNC 2017 [10] corpora available in Sketch Engine. For a detailed description of the evaluation, see [1].

The evaluation of the thesauri is clearly just a starting point but it already shows that none of the variants (thesaurus based on word sketches and thesaurus based on word embeddings) outperforms the other one for all languages.

6 Conclusions and future development

In this paper we have described recent developments of the HAMOD dataset. We argued why such a dataset is necessary for further development, evaluation and comparison of distributional thesauri and we have discussed the current status of the dataset. We plan to further expand the dataset to reach 100 exercise sets and cover more languages (EU languages in the first place) while continuously monitoring the inter-annotator agreement and adjusting the dataset accordingly to maintain high agreement. So far the discriminative power of the dataset (i.e. its ability to discover differences between individual thesaurus types) is maintained as well but we are aware of the fact that at

Table 2: Comparison of a Sketch Engine-based and word-embeddings-based thesaurus on the HAMOD dataset. Dataset size means number of exercises (outlier detection exercise sets) that were evaluated.

Corpus	Corpus size	Dataset size	SkE Acc	SkE OPP	Word2Vec Acc	Word2vec OPP
czTenTen12	5G	232	0.573	0.898	0.655	0.871
enTenTen13	22G	296	0.456	0.847	0.655	0.873
EstonianNC 2017	1.3G	296	0.564	0.832	0.547	0.784
deTenTen13	19G	232	0.349	0.798	0.323	0.764
frTenTen12	6.8G	232	0.276	0.744	0.427	0.768
skTenTen11	0.6G	296	0.389	0.777	0.591	0.851
itTenTen16	5.8G	296	0.453	0.856	0.581	0.869

some point of further development of the thesauri the dataset might need to be revisited if it loses its discriminative power, i.e. if it would be a task too easy for the computer. When finished the dataset will become available under a permissible Creative Commons licence in a public repository.

Fig. 3: A sample outlier detection exercise generated for English.

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